

POSITIVE SOLUTIONS FOR NONLINEAR SINGULAR PROBLEMS WITH SIGN-CHANGING NONLINEARITIES

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*Dedicated to Professor Vicențiu D. Rădulescu
on the occasion of his 65th birthday.*

ABSTRACT. We consider a Dirichlet problem driven by a general nonlinear, nonhomogeneous differential operator. The reaction has the competing effects of a singular term and of a parametric perturbation which is superlinear and sign-changing. Using variational tools from critical point theory together with truncation and comparison techniques, we show that for all small values of the parameter, the problem has at least two positive smooth solutions. Also, we show the existence of a smallest positive solution (minimal positive solution).

1. Introduction. Let $\Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}^N$ be a bounded domain with a C^2 -boundary $\partial\Omega$. In this paper, we study the following nonlinear singular problem

$$\begin{cases} -\operatorname{div}(Du(z)) = u(z)^{-\eta} + \lambda f(z, u(z)) & \text{in } \Omega, \\ u = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega, \\ u > 0 & \text{in } \Omega, \end{cases} \quad (1.1)$$

with $\lambda > 0$ and $0 < \eta < 1$. In this problem, the map $a: \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^N$ involved in the definition of the differential operator is continuous, strictly monotone (hence maximal monotone too), and satisfies certain other regularity and growth conditions listed in hypotheses H_0 below. These conditions provide a general framework in which we can fit many differential operators of interest such as the p -Laplacian and the (p, q) -Laplacian (double phase problems with balanced growth). In the reaction (right hand side) of (1.1), we have the combined effects of a singular term $u^{-\eta}$ and of a parametric perturbation $\lambda f(z, u)$ with $\lambda > 0$ being the parameter and $f(\cdot, \cdot)$

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being a Carathéodory function (that is, for all $x \in \mathbb{R}$, $z \mapsto f(z, x)$ is measurable, and for a.a. $z \in \Omega$, $x \mapsto f(z, x)$ is continuous) which exhibits $(p - 1)$ -superlinear growth as $x \rightarrow +\infty$, but need not satisfy the Ambrosetti-Rabinowitz condition (the AR-condition, for short) which is common in the literature when dealing with superlinear problems.

This kind of singular problems, was investigated by Papageorgiou-Winkert [18] for equations driven by the p -Laplacian and with a positive perturbation $f(z, x)$. In that setting the unique positive solution of the purely singular problem serves as a lower solution for (1.1). Using it, we can bypass the singularity and deal with C^1 -functionals on which we can use the tools from the critical point theory (see also Bai-Papageorgiou-Zeng [1], who studied singular eigenvalue problems and Papageorgiou-Rădulescu-Repovš [16] who studied singular problems involving the parameters in the singular term). If $f(\cdot, \cdot)$ is sign changing, then the above approach fails and we need to come up with a new method in order to have a result on the existence and multiplicity of positive solutions for problem (1.1).

2. Mathematical background & hypotheses. In the analysis of problem (1.1), the main spaces are the Sobolev space $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ and the Banach space $C_0^1(\bar{\Omega}) := \{u \in C^1(\bar{\Omega}) \mid u = 0 \text{ on } \partial\Omega\}$. The Poincaré inequality implies that on $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$, so, we can use the equivalent norm

$$\|u\| = \|Du\|_p \text{ for all } u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega).$$

The Banach space $C_0^1(\bar{\Omega})$ is ordered with positive (order) cone

$$C_+ := \{u \in C^1(\bar{\Omega}) \mid 0 \leq u(z) \text{ for all } z \in \bar{\Omega}\}.$$

This cone has a nonempty interior set given by

$$\text{int}C_+ := \left\{ u \in C_+ \mid u(z) > 0 \text{ for all } z \in \Omega \text{ and } \frac{\partial u}{\partial n} \Big|_{\partial\Omega} < 0 \right\},$$

with $\frac{\partial u}{\partial n} = (Du, n)_{\mathbb{R}^N}$, where $n(\cdot)$ is the outward unit normal on $\partial\Omega$.

If $u, v: \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are two measurable functions and $u(z) \leq v(z)$ for a.a. $z \in \Omega$, then we define the following sets

$$[u, v] := \{g \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \mid u(z) \leq g(z) \leq v(z) \text{ for a.a. } z \in \Omega\},$$

$$\text{int}[u, v] := \text{the interior in } C_0^1(\bar{\Omega}) \text{ of } [u, v] \cap C_0^1(\bar{\Omega}),$$

$$[u] := \left\{ h \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \mid u(z) \leq h(z) \text{ for a.a. } z \in \Omega \right\}.$$

For a measurable function $u: \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, we define

$$u^\pm(z) = \max\{\pm u(z), 0\} \text{ for all } z \in \Omega.$$

We have $u = u^+ - u^-$, $|u| = u^+ + u^-$ and if $u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$, then $u^\pm \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$.

Let X be a Banach space and $\varphi \in C^1(X, \mathbb{R})$. We set

$$K_\varphi := \{u \in X \mid \varphi'(u) = 0\} \text{ (the critical set of } \varphi).$$

We say that $\varphi(\cdot)$ satisfies the ‘‘C-condition’’, if the following is true:

- ‘‘every sequence $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq X$ such that
- $\{\varphi(u_n)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ is bounded,
 - $(1 + \|u_n\|_X)\varphi'(u_n) \rightarrow 0$ in X^* as $n \rightarrow \infty$,
- admits a strongly convergent subsequence’’.

Let $\theta \in C^1(0, \infty)$ be such that $\theta(t) > 0$ for all $t > 0$ and satisfies the following inequalities

$$0 < c \leq \frac{t\theta'(t)}{\theta(t)} \leq \hat{c} \quad \text{and} \quad c_0 t^{p-1} \leq \theta(t) \leq c_1 [t^{s-1} + t^{p-1}]$$

for all $t \geq 0$, with some $c_0, c_1 > 0$ and $1 < s < p$. The hypotheses on the map $a(\cdot)$ are the following:

\underline{H}_0 : $a(y) = a_0(|y|)y$ for all $y \in \mathbb{R}^N$ with $a_0(t) > 0$ for all $t > 0$ and

- (i) $a_0 \in C^1(0, \infty)$, $t \mapsto a_0(t)t$ is strictly increasing on $(0, +\infty)$, $a_0(t)t \rightarrow 0^+$ as $t \rightarrow 0^+$ and $-1 < \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{a_0'(t)t}{a_0(t)}$;
- (ii) $|\nabla a(y)| \leq c_2 \frac{\theta(|y|)}{|y|}$ for all $y \in \mathbb{R}^N \setminus \{0\}$, with some $c_2 > 0$;
- (iii) $\frac{\theta(|y|)}{|y|} |\xi|^2 \leq (\nabla a(y)\xi, \xi)_{\mathbb{R}^N}$ for all $y \in \mathbb{R}^N \setminus \{0\}$ and all $\xi \in \mathbb{R}^N$;
- (iv) if $G_0(t) = \int_0^t a_0(s)s ds$ for all $t \geq 0$, then there exists $q \in (1, p)$ such that $t \mapsto G_0(t^{\frac{1}{q}})$ is convex on $[0, +\infty)$, $\lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{G_0(t)}{t^q} \leq c^*$ and $pG_0(t) - a_0(t)t^2 \geq 0$ for all $t \geq 0$.

Remark 2.1. The nonlinear regularity theory has two major steps. First, we show that the weak solution is in $L^\infty(\Omega)$ and in fact the $L^\infty(\Omega)$ norm is bounded independently of the solution, if the latter is $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ -bounded and then, we can claim that the solutions are $C_0^{1,\alpha}(\bar{\Omega})$ ($0 < \alpha < 1$) with the norm bounded uniformly. For the $L^\infty(\Omega)$ -part, we use the results of Ladyzhenskaya-Ural'tseva [10], Theorem 7.1, p. 286 and Papageorgiou-Rădulescu [14], Proposition 2.10 (uniform bound of the L^∞ -norms) and then the theory of Lieberman [12] (p. 320) applies and provides the desired global Hölder continuity of the solutions. The moment, we have this continuity, under appropriate assumptions on the reaction (see hypothesis H_1 (iv)), we can use Theorem 5.5.1, p. 120 of Pucci-Serrin [19] (the nonlinear Hopf maximum principle), to conclude that the solution is in $\text{int}C_+$. Hypotheses H_0 (i)–(iii) are motivated by the nonlinear regularity theory of Lieberman [12] and the nonlinear maximum principle of Pucci-Serrin [19]. These hypotheses guarantee that the positive solutions are in C_+ (see, for example Lieberman [12]) and then the nonlinear maximum principle (see Pucci-Serrin [19]) gives that the positive solutions are in $\text{int}C_+$. Hypothesis H_0 (iv) serves the particular needs of our problem, but it is not restrictive and it is satisfied in all the cases of interest (see the Examples below). Similar conditions on the differential operator can be found in Papageorgiou-Rădulescu-Repovš [16].

Hypotheses H_0 imply that the primitive $G_0(\cdot)$ is strictly increasing and strictly convex. We set $G(y) = G_0(|y|)$ for all $y \in \mathbb{R}^N$. Also, we have

$$\nabla G(y) = G_0'(|y|) \frac{y}{|y|} = a_0(|y|)y = a(y) \quad \text{for all } y \in \mathbb{R}^N \setminus \{0\}.$$

Moreover, we have $\nabla G(0) = 0$ (see hypothesis H_0 (i)). So, the function $G(\cdot)$ is the primitive of $a(\cdot)$, and since $G(\cdot)$ is convex, from the properties of convex functions, we have

$$G(y) \leq (a(y), y)_{\mathbb{R}^N} \quad \text{for all } y \in \mathbb{R}^N. \quad (2.1)$$

The next lemma summarizes the main properties of the map $a(\cdot)$ (see Papageorgiou-Rădulescu [13]).

Lemma 2.2. *If hypotheses H_0 (i)–(iii) hold, then we have*

- (a) $y \mapsto a(y)$ is continuous, strictly monotone, thus maximal monotone too;
- (b) $|a(y)| \leq c_3 [|y|^{s-1} + |y|^{p-1}]$ for all $y \in \mathbb{R}^N$, some $c_3 > 0$;
- (c) $\frac{c_0}{p-1} |y|^p \leq (a(y), y)_{\mathbb{R}^N}$ for all $y \in \mathbb{R}^N$.

This lemma combined with (2.1), leads to the following bilateral growth conditions for the primitive $G(\cdot)$.

Corollary 2.3. *If hypotheses H_0 (i)–(iii) hold, then*

$$\frac{c_0}{p(p-1)} |y|^p \leq G(y) \leq c_4 [|y|^s + |y|^p] \text{ for all } y \in \mathbb{R}^N$$

with some $c_4 > 0$.

Remark 2.4. This corollary reveals that $G(\cdot)$ exhibits balanced growth and so the global (up to the boundary) regularity theory of Lieberman [12] applies to our problem.

The examples which follow, illustrate that the framework provided by hypotheses H_0 is broad and incorporates many differential operators of interest.

Example 2.5. The following maps satisfy hypotheses H_0 (see [14]):

- (a) $a(y) = |y|^{p-2}y$ with $1 < p < \infty$. This map corresponds to the p -Laplace differential operator

$$\Delta_p u = \operatorname{div}(|Du|^{p-2}Du) \text{ for all } u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega).$$

- (b) $a(y) = |y|^{p-2}y + |y|^{q-2}y$ with $1 < q < p$. This map corresponds to the (p, q) -Laplace differential operator (double phase differential operator with balanced growth)

$$\Delta_p u + \Delta_q u \text{ for all } u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega).$$

- (c) $a(y) = [1 + |y|^2]^{\frac{p-2}{2}}y$ with $1 < p < \infty$. This map corresponds to the generalized p -mean curvature differential operator

$$\operatorname{div} \left((1 + |Du|^2)^{\frac{p-2}{2}} Du \right) \text{ for all } u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega).$$

- (d) $a(y) = |y|^{p-2}y \left[1 + \frac{1}{1 + |y|^p} \right]$ with $1 < p < \infty$. This map corresponds to the operator

$$\Delta_p u + \operatorname{div} \left(\frac{|Du|^{p-2}Du}{1 + |Du|^p} \right) \text{ for all } u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega),$$

which arises in problems of plasticity theory (see Roubiřek [20]).

Let $V : W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \rightarrow W^{-1,p'}(\Omega) =: W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)^*$ with $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{p'} = 1$ be the nonlinear operator defined by

$$\langle V(u), h \rangle := \int_{\Omega} (a(Du), Dh)_{\mathbb{R}^N} dz \text{ for all } u, h \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega).$$

From Gasiński-Papageorgiou [6] (p. 279), we have the following result listing the main properties of the map $V(\cdot)$

Proposition 2.6. *If hypotheses H_0 (i)–(iii) hold, then $V : W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \rightarrow W^{-1,p'}(\Omega)$ is bounded (that is, it maps bounded sets to bounded sets), continuous, strictly monotone (hence maximal monotone too) and of type $(S)_+$, that is,*

$$\text{if } u_n \xrightarrow{w} u \text{ in } W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \text{ and } \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle V(u_n), u_n - u \rangle \leq 0,$$

imply that $u_n \rightarrow u$ in $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$.

The hypotheses on the perturbation $f(\cdot, \cdot)$ are the following (note that in the sequel a.a. stand for “almost all”):

H_1 : $f : \Omega \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a Carathéodory such that $f(z, 0) = 0$ for a.a. $z \in \Omega$ and

- (i) $|f(z, x)| \leq \alpha(z) [1 + x^{r-1}]$ for a.a. $z \in \Omega$, all $x \geq 0$ with $\alpha \in L^\infty(\Omega)$, $p < r < p^*$, where p^* is defined by

$$p^* := \begin{cases} \frac{Np}{N-p} & \text{if } p < N, \\ +\infty & \text{if } N \leq p, \end{cases} ;$$

- (ii) if $F(z, x) := \int_0^x f(z, s) ds$, then $\lim_{x \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{F(z, x)}{x^p} = +\infty$ uniformly for a.a. $z \in \Omega$;

- (iii) there exists $\tau \in \left((r-p) \max\{\frac{N}{p}, 1\}, p^* \right)$ such that

$$0 < \beta_0 \leq \liminf_{x \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{f(z, x)x - pF(z, x)}{x^\tau} \text{ uniformly for a.a. } z \in \Omega;$$

- (iii) $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} f(z, x) = 0$ uniformly for a.a. $z \in \Omega$ and there exists $c^* > 0$ such that $f(z, x) + x^{-\eta} \geq c^* > 0$ for a.a. $z \in \Omega$ and all $x > 0$;

- (iv) let $q \in (1, p)$ as in hypothesis H_0 (iv), we have

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{f(z, x)}{x^{q-1}} = +\infty \text{ uniformly for a.a. } z \in \Omega,$$

and for every $\rho > 0$, there exists $\hat{\xi}_\rho > 0$ such that for a.a. $z \in \Omega$ the function $x \mapsto f(z, x) + \hat{\xi}_\rho x^{p-1}$ is nondecreasing on $[0, \rho]$.

Remark 2.7. Since we are looking for positive solutions and all the above hypotheses concern the positive semiaxis $\mathbb{R}_+ = [0, +\infty)$, we may assume without any loss of generality that

$$f(z, x) = 0 \text{ for a.a. } z \in \Omega \text{ and all } x \leq 0.$$

Hypotheses H (ii) and (iii) imply that

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{f(z, x)}{x^{p-1}} = +\infty \text{ uniformly for a.a. } z \in \Omega.$$

This means that the perturbation $f(z, \cdot)$ is $(p-1)$ -superlinear as $x \rightarrow +\infty$. Usually superlinear problems are treated using the so-called Ambrosetti-Rabinowitz condition (the AR-condition, for short), see Chang [2], p. 147 and Willem [21], p. 59. Using this condition, it is straightforward to satisfy the compactness condition (the C -condition) for the energy functional of the problem. Here instead of the AR-condition, we employ the less restrictive hypothesis H_1 (iii), which incorporates in our setting also superlinear functions with “slower” growth near $+\infty$ which fail to satisfy the AR-condition (see the example below). We stress that we do not impose any sign condition on the perturbation f . In fact, f may change sign and only near zero and near $+\infty$ is positive (see H_1 (ii) and (iv)).

Example 2.8. The following function satisfies hypotheses H_1 , but fails to satisfy the AR-condition. For the sake of simplicity, we drop the z -dependence

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} (x^+)^{q-1}[1 - \ln x^+] - c(x^+)^{\tau-1} & \text{if } x \leq 1, \\ x^{p-1} \ln x + (1-c)x^{\mu-1} & \text{if } 1 \leq x, \end{cases}$$

with $1 < q < \tau$, $1 < \mu < p$ and $c > 1$. Note that $f(\cdot)$ changes sign.

3. Auxiliary problems. Hypotheses H_1 (i) and (iv) imply that given any $\eta > 0$, we can find $c_5 = c_5(\eta) > 0$ such that

$$f(z, x) \geq \eta x^{q-1} - c_5 x^{r-1} \quad \text{for a.a. } z \in \Omega, \quad \text{all } x \geq 0. \quad (3.1)$$

This unilateral growth condition on $f(z, \cdot)$ leads to the following auxiliary Dirichlet problem

$$\begin{cases} -\operatorname{div}(Du(z)) = \lambda[\eta u(z)^{q-1} - c_5 u(z)^{r-1}] & \text{in } \Omega, \\ u = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega, \\ u > 0 & \text{in } \Omega, \end{cases} \quad (3.2)$$

with $\lambda > 0$.

Proposition 3.1. *If hypotheses H_0 hold and $1 < q < p < r$, then for all $\eta > 0$ large and for all $\lambda > 0$, problem (3.2) has a unique positive solution $\bar{u}_\lambda \in \operatorname{int}C_+$ and*

$$\bar{u}_\lambda \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{in } C_0^1(\bar{\Omega}) \quad \text{as } \lambda \rightarrow 0^+.$$

Proof. First, we show the existence of a positive solution for (3.2) with $\lambda > 0$, when $\eta > 0$ is large. To this end, we introduce the C^1 -functional $\psi_\lambda: W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined by

$$\psi_\lambda(u) := \int_\Omega G(Du) dz + \frac{\lambda c_5}{r} \|u^+\|_r^r - \frac{\lambda \eta}{q} \|u^+\|_q^q \quad \text{for all } u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega).$$

Using Corollary 2.3 and the fact that $q < r$, we see that $\psi_\lambda(\cdot)$ is coercive. The sequential weak lower semicontinuity of the convex integral functional $u \mapsto \int_\Omega G(Du) dz$ and the Sobolev embedding theorem, imply that $\psi_\lambda(\cdot)$ is sequentially weakly lower semicontinuous. By the Weierstrass-Tonelli theorem, we can find $\bar{u}_\lambda \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ such that

$$\psi_\lambda(\bar{u}_\lambda) = \inf \left[\psi_\lambda(u) \mid u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \right].$$

From hypothesis H_0 (iv), we see that given $c_6 > c^*$ there is $\delta > 0$ such that

$$0 \leq G(y) \leq c_6 |y|^q \quad \text{for all } |y| \leq \delta. \quad (3.3)$$

Let $\hat{u}_1(q)$ be the positive, L^q -normalized eigenfunction corresponding to the principal eigenvalue $\hat{\lambda}_1(q) > 0$ of $(-\Delta_q, W_0^{1,q}(\Omega))$. We know that $\hat{u}_1(q) \in \operatorname{int}C_+$ (see Gasiński-Papageorgiou [5]). Choose $t \in (0, 1)$ small so that

$$0 \leq t\hat{u}_1(q)(z) \leq \delta \quad \text{for all } z \in \bar{\Omega}. \quad (3.4)$$

Using (3.3)–(3.4) and the fact $\|\hat{u}_1(q)\|_q = 1$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_\lambda(t\hat{u}_1(q)) &\leq c_6 t^q \|D\hat{u}_1(q)\|_q^q - \lambda \eta t^q + \lambda c_5 t^r \|\hat{u}_1(q)\|_r^r \\ &= t^q \left[c_6 \hat{\lambda}_1(q) - \lambda \eta \right] + \lambda c_5 t^r \|\hat{u}_1(q)\|_r^r. \end{aligned}$$

Since $\eta > 0$ is arbitrary, we choose $\eta > \frac{c_6 \hat{\lambda}_1(q)}{\lambda}$ and obtain

$$\psi_\lambda(t\hat{u}_1(q)) \leq c_7 t^r - c_8 t^q \text{ for some } c_7, c_8 > 0.$$

But $q < p < r$. So, choosing $t \in (0, 1)$ even smaller if necessary, we have

$$\psi_\lambda(t\hat{u}_1(q)) < 0 \Rightarrow \psi_\lambda(\bar{u}_\lambda) < 0 = \psi_\lambda(0) \text{ (see (3.2))} \Rightarrow \bar{u}_\lambda \neq 0.$$

From (3.2), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \psi'_\lambda(\bar{u}_\lambda), h \rangle &= 0 \text{ for all } h \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \Rightarrow \\ \langle V(\bar{u}_\lambda), h \rangle &= \lambda \int_\Omega \left[\eta \bar{u}_\lambda^{q-1} - c_5 \bar{u}_\lambda^{r-1} \right] h \, dz \end{aligned} \quad (3.5)$$

for all $h \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$. In (3.5), we choose the test function $h = -\bar{u}_\lambda^- \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$. Using Lemma 2.2, we obtain

$$\frac{c_0}{p-1} \|D\bar{u}_\lambda^-\|_p^p \leq 0 \Rightarrow \bar{u}_\lambda \geq 0 \text{ and } \bar{u}_\lambda \neq 0.$$

From (3.5), we have

$$\begin{cases} -\operatorname{div}(D\bar{u}_\lambda) = \lambda \left[\eta \bar{u}_\lambda^{q-1} - c_5 \bar{u}_\lambda^{r-1} \right] & \text{in } \Omega, \\ \bar{u}_\lambda = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega. \end{cases}$$

By Theorem 7.1, p. 286, of Ladyzhenskaya-Uraltseva [10] (see also [14]), we have $\bar{u}_\lambda \in L^\infty(\Omega)$. Then, using the nonlinear regularity theory of Lieberman [12, p. 320], we have that $\bar{u}_\lambda \in C_+ \setminus \{0\}$. Let $\rho = \|\bar{u}_\lambda\|_\infty$. Since $q < r$, we can find $\xi_\rho^* > 0$ such that

$$0 \leq \lambda \left[\eta x^{q-1} - c_5 x^{r-1} \right] + \xi_\rho^* x^{p-1} \text{ for a.a. } z \in \Omega \text{ and for all } 0 \leq x \leq \rho. \quad (3.6)$$

Using (3.6), we have

$$-\operatorname{div}(D\bar{u}_\lambda) + \xi_\rho^* \bar{u}_\lambda^{p-1} \geq 0 \text{ in } \Omega \Rightarrow \operatorname{div}(D\bar{u}_\lambda) \leq \xi_\rho^* \bar{u}_\lambda^{p-1} \text{ in } \Omega.$$

Using the nonlinear maximum principle of Pucci-Serrin [19] (p. 120), we have

$$\bar{u}_\lambda \in \operatorname{int}C_+.$$

Next we show the uniqueness of this positive solution. For this purpose, we introduce the integral functional $j: L^1(\Omega) \rightarrow \bar{\mathbb{R}} = \mathbb{R} \cup \{\infty\}$ defined by

$$j(u) = \begin{cases} \int_\Omega G(Du^{\frac{1}{q}}) \, dz & \text{if } u \geq 0 \text{ and } u^{\frac{1}{q}} \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega), \\ +\infty & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Let $\operatorname{dom}j := \{u \in L^1(\Omega) \mid j(u) < \infty\}$ (the effective domain of $j(\cdot)$). For $u_1, u_2 \in \operatorname{dom}j$, we set $u = [tu_1 + (1-t)u_2]^{\frac{1}{q}}$ with $t \in [0, 1]$. From Diaz-Saa [3] and hypothesis $H_0(\text{iv})$, using the monotonicity of $G_0(\cdot)$ we get

$$|Du(z)| \leq \left[t|Du_1^{\frac{1}{q}}|^q + (1-t)|Du_2^{\frac{1}{q}}|^q \right]^{\frac{1}{q}},$$

thus,

$$\begin{aligned} G_0(|Du(z)|) &\leq G_0 \left(\left(t|Du_1^{\frac{1}{q}}|^q + (1-t)|Du_2^{\frac{1}{q}}|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right) \\ &\leq tG_0(|Du_1^{\frac{1}{q}}|) + (1-t)G_0(|Du_2^{\frac{1}{q}}|). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, we have

$$G(Du(z)) \leq tG(Du_1(z)^{\frac{1}{q}}) + (1-t)G(Du_2(z)^{\frac{1}{q}}) \Rightarrow j(\cdot) \text{ is convex.}$$

Let $\bar{v}_\lambda \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ be another positive solution of (3.2). As before, the nonlinear regularity theory (see [12]) and the nonlinear maximum principle (see [19]), imply that $\bar{v}_\lambda \in \text{int}C_+$. Then, on account of Proposition 4.1.22, p. 274, of Papageorgiou-Rădulescu-Repovš [15], we have

$$\frac{\bar{u}_\lambda}{\bar{v}_\lambda} \in L^\infty(\Omega) \text{ and } \frac{\bar{v}_\lambda}{\bar{u}_\lambda} \in L^\infty(\Omega). \quad (3.7)$$

Let $h = \bar{u}_\lambda^q - \bar{v}_\lambda^q \in C_0^1(\bar{\Omega})$. From (3.7), we see that for $t \in (0, 1)$ small it holds

$$\bar{u}_\lambda^q + th \in \text{dom}j \text{ and } \bar{v}_\lambda^q + th \in \text{dom}j.$$

This fact and the convexity of $j(\cdot)$, imply that the directional derivatives of $j(\cdot)$ at \bar{u}_λ^q and at \bar{v}_λ^q in the direction h exist. Then, using Green's identity, we have

$$j'(\bar{u}_\lambda^q)(h) = \frac{1}{q} \int_\Omega \frac{-\text{diva}(D\bar{u}_\lambda)}{\bar{u}_\lambda^{q-1}} h \, dz = \frac{1}{q} \int_\Omega \lambda [\eta - c_5 \bar{u}_\lambda^{r-q}] h \, dz,$$

and

$$j'(\bar{v}_\lambda^q)(h) = \frac{1}{q} \int_\Omega \frac{-\text{diva}(D\bar{v}_\lambda)}{\bar{v}_\lambda^{q-1}} h \, dz = \frac{1}{q} \int_\Omega \lambda [\eta - c_5 \bar{v}_\lambda^{r-q}] h \, dz.$$

The convexity of $j(\cdot)$ implies the monotonicity of $j'(\cdot)$. Hence,

$$0 \leq \frac{\lambda}{q} \int_\Omega c_5 [\bar{v}_\lambda^{r-q} - \bar{u}_\lambda^{r-q}] (\bar{u}_\lambda^q - \bar{v}_\lambda^q) \, dz \leq 0 \Rightarrow \bar{u}_\lambda = \bar{v}_\lambda.$$

This proves the uniqueness of the positive solution $\bar{u}_\lambda \in \text{int}C_+$ of problem (3.2).

For every $\lambda > 0$, we have

$$-\text{diva}(D\bar{u}_\lambda) = \lambda [\eta \bar{u}_\lambda^{q-1} - c_5 \bar{u}_\lambda^{r-1}] \text{ in } \Omega.$$

We act with $\bar{u}_\lambda \in \text{int}C_+$ and use Lemma 2.2 to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{c_0}{p-1} \|D\bar{u}_\lambda\|_p^p &\leq \lambda \eta \|\bar{u}_\lambda\|_q^q \\ \Rightarrow \frac{c_0}{p-1} \|\bar{u}_\lambda\|^p &\leq \lambda \eta c_9 \|\bar{u}_\lambda\|^q \text{ for some } c_9 > 0 \\ \Rightarrow \frac{c_0}{p-1} \|\bar{u}_\lambda\|^{p-q} &\leq \lambda \eta c_9, \end{aligned} \quad (3.8)$$

where we have used the fact that $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \hookrightarrow L^q(\Omega)$ is continuous. Since $q < p$ (see $H_0(\text{iv})$), we see that

$$\{\bar{u}_\lambda\}_{\lambda \in (0,1]} \subseteq W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \text{ is bounded.}$$

This then implies that

$$\|\bar{u}_\lambda\|_\infty \leq c_{10} \text{ for some } c_{10} > 0 \text{ and for all } \lambda \in (0, 1],$$

where we have used the results, Theorem 7.1 of Ladyzhenskaya-Ural'tseva [10], p. 286, and Theorem 2.10 of Papageorgiou-Rădulescu [14], which guarantees that the L^∞ -norms of these solutions are uniformly bounded. Then, the nonlinear regularity theory of Lieberman [12, p. 320], implies that there exist $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ and $c_{11} > 0$ such that

$$\bar{u}_\lambda \in C_0^{1,\alpha}(\bar{\Omega}) \text{ and } \|\bar{u}_\lambda\|_{C_0^{1,\alpha}(\bar{\Omega})} \leq c_{11} \text{ for all } \lambda \in (0, 1], \quad (3.9)$$

because $\{\bar{u}_\lambda\}_{\lambda \in (0,1]} \subset L^\infty(\Omega)$ is bounded. From (3.8), we see that $\bar{u}_\lambda \rightarrow 0$ in $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ as $\lambda \rightarrow 0^+$. Then, (3.9) and the compact embedding of $C_0^{1,\alpha}(\bar{\Omega})$ into $C_0^1(\bar{\Omega})$, imply that $\bar{u}_\lambda \rightarrow 0$ in $C_0^1(\bar{\Omega})$ as $\lambda \rightarrow 0^+$. \square

Let $\hat{d}(z) = d(z, \partial\Omega)$. Then, since $\bar{u}_\lambda \in \text{int}C_+$ and using Lemma 14.16, p. 355, of Gilbarg-Trudinger [8], we can find $c_{12}, c_{13} > 0$ such that

$$c_{12}\hat{d} \leq \bar{u}_\lambda \leq c_{13}\hat{d}. \quad (3.10)$$

For $h \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} \frac{|h|}{\bar{u}_\lambda^\eta} dz &= \int_{\Omega} \bar{u}_\lambda^{1-\eta} \frac{|h|}{\bar{u}_\lambda} dz \\ &\leq c_{14} \int_{\Omega} \frac{|h|}{\bar{u}_\lambda} dz \text{ for some } c_{14} > 0 \text{ (recall } \bar{u}_\lambda \in \text{int}C_+) \\ &\leq c_{15} \int_{\Omega} \frac{|h|}{\hat{d}} dz \text{ for some } c_{15} > 0 \text{ (see (3.10))} \\ &\leq c_{16} \left[\int_{\Omega} \left(\frac{|h|}{\hat{d}} \right)^p dz \right]^{\frac{1}{p}} \text{ for some } c_{16} > 0 \\ &\leq c_{17} \|Dh\|_p \text{ for some } c_{17} > 0, \end{aligned}$$

where we have used the continuity of the embedding $L^p(\Omega) \hookrightarrow L^1(\Omega)$ and Hardy's inequality (see [15], p. 66). Hence,

$$\bar{u}_\lambda^{-\eta} \in W^{-1,p'}(\Omega) = W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)^*.$$

We consider the following auxiliary Dirichlet problem

$$\begin{cases} -\text{div}_a(Du(z)) = \bar{u}_\lambda(z)^{-\eta} + 1 & \text{in } \Omega, \\ u = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega. \end{cases} \quad (3.11)$$

Proposition 3.2. *For every $\lambda > 0$, problem (3.11) has a unique solution*

$$\tilde{u}_\lambda \in \text{int}C_+.$$

Proof. From Proposition 2.6, we know that the operator $V(\cdot)$ is maximal monotone. Using Lemma 2.2, we have

$$\frac{c_0}{p-1} \|u\|^p \leq \langle V(u), u \rangle \text{ for all } u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \quad \Rightarrow \quad V(\cdot) \text{ is coercive.}$$

But a maximal monotone, coercive operator is surjective (see [15], p. 135). So, we can find $\tilde{u}_\lambda \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ such that

$$V(\tilde{u}_\lambda) = \bar{u}_\lambda^{-\eta} + 1 \in W^{-1,p'}(\Omega).$$

Moreover, the strict monotonicity of $V(\cdot)$ (see Proposition 2.6) implies that this solution is unique. On account of (3.10), we have

$$c_{18}\hat{d}^{-\eta} \leq \bar{u}_\lambda^{-\eta} + 1 \leq c_{19}\hat{d}^{-\eta}$$

for some $c_{18}, c_{19} > 0$. Then, using (3.10) and Theorem 1.7 of Giacomoni-Kumar-Sreenadh [7], (note that the results of [7] is for more general nonautonomous differential operators) we have that $\tilde{u}_\lambda \in C_+ \setminus \{0\}$ and

$$\text{div}_a(D\tilde{u}_\lambda) \leq 0 \text{ in } \Omega.$$

Therefore, from Pucci-Serrin [19], we obtain $\tilde{u}_\lambda \in \text{int}C_+$. \square

The family $\{\tilde{u}_\lambda\}_{\lambda>0}$ of solutions of (3.11) is bounded in $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$. Note that by (3.10) and the Lemma of Lazer-McKenna [11], we have $\bar{u}_\lambda^{-\eta} + 1 \in W^{-1,p'}(\Omega) \cap L^1(\Omega)$. Also, we have

$$\langle V(\tilde{u}_\lambda), h \rangle = \int_{\Omega} [\bar{u}_\lambda^{-\eta} + 1] h \, dz$$

for all $h \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$. Choosing $h = \tilde{u}_\lambda \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$, we have,

$$\frac{c_0}{p-1} \|D\tilde{u}_\lambda\|_p^p \leq \int_{\Omega} \left[\frac{\tilde{u}_\lambda}{\bar{u}_\lambda^\eta} + \tilde{u}_\lambda \right] dz \leq M \|\tilde{u}_\lambda\|$$

for some $M > 0$ (we have used Hardy's inequality). Then, it holds $\|\tilde{u}_\lambda\|^{p-1} \leq \hat{M}$ for some $\hat{M} > 0$. So, by the nonlinear regularity theory and hypothesis $H_1(i)$, we can find $\lambda_0 \in (0, 1]$ such that

$$\lambda \max \{f(z, \bar{u}_\lambda(z)), f(z, \tilde{u}_\lambda(z))\} \leq \theta_0 < 1 \quad (3.12)$$

for a.a. $z \in \Omega$ and for all $\lambda \in (0, \lambda_0]$.

Proposition 3.3. *If $\lambda \in (0, \lambda_0)$, then $\bar{u}_\lambda \leq \tilde{u}_\lambda$.*

Proof. We have

$$\begin{aligned} -\operatorname{diva}(D\tilde{u}_\lambda) &= \bar{u}_\lambda^{-\eta} + 1 \\ &\geq \lambda f(z, \bar{u}_\lambda) \quad (\text{see (3.12)}) \\ &\geq \lambda \left[\eta \bar{u}_\lambda^{q-1} - c_5 \bar{u}_\lambda^{r-1} \right] \quad (\text{see (3.1)}) \\ &= -\operatorname{diva}(D\bar{u}_\lambda). \end{aligned}$$

Acting with $(\bar{u}_\lambda - \tilde{u}_\lambda)^+ \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$, we obtain

$$0 \leq \int_{\{\bar{u}_\lambda \geq \tilde{u}_\lambda\}} (a(D\bar{u}) - a(D\tilde{u}_\lambda), D\bar{u}_\lambda - D(\tilde{u}_\lambda))_{\mathbb{R}^N} dz \quad \Rightarrow \quad |\{\bar{u}_\lambda > \tilde{u}_\lambda\}|_N = 0,$$

where $|\cdot|_N$ is the Lebesgue measure on \mathbb{R}^N , see Lemma 2.2. Hence, we get $\bar{u}_\lambda \leq \tilde{u}_\lambda$. \square

4. Positive solutions. We introduce the following two sets:

$$\mathcal{L} = \{ \lambda > 0 \mid \text{problem (1.1) has a positive solution} \},$$

and

$$S_\lambda = \text{set of positive solutions of (1.1)}.$$

Fix $\lambda \in (0, \lambda_0]$ and based on Proposition 3.3, we introduce the Carathéodory function \hat{k}_λ defined by

$$\hat{k}_\lambda(z, x) := \begin{cases} \bar{u}_\lambda(z)^{-\eta} + \lambda f(z, \bar{u}_\lambda(z)) & \text{if } x < \bar{u}_\lambda(z), \\ x^{-\eta} + \lambda f(z, x) & \text{if } \bar{u}_\lambda(z) \leq x \leq \tilde{u}_\lambda(z), \\ \tilde{u}_\lambda(z)^{-\eta} + \lambda f(z, \tilde{u}_\lambda) & \text{if } \tilde{u}_\lambda(z) < x. \end{cases} \quad (4.1)$$

We set $\hat{K}_\lambda(z, x) := \int_0^x \hat{k}_\lambda(z, s) \, ds$ and consider the C^1 -functional $\hat{\varphi}_\lambda: W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined by

$$\hat{\varphi}_\lambda(u) := \int_{\Omega} G(Du) \, dz - \int_{\Omega} \hat{K}_\lambda(z, u) \, dz \quad \text{for all } u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega).$$

In the next proposition using the functional $\hat{\varphi}_\lambda(\cdot)$ with $\lambda \in (0, \lambda_0]$, we show that $\mathcal{L} \neq \emptyset$ and determine the regularity of the elements of S_λ .

Proposition 4.1. *If hypotheses H_0, H_1 hold, then $\mathcal{L} \neq \emptyset$ and $S_\lambda \subseteq \text{int}C_+$.*

Proof. Let $\lambda \in (0, \lambda_0]$ consider the functional $\hat{\varphi}_\lambda \in C^1(W_0^{1,p}(\Omega); \mathbb{R})$ defined above. From (4.1), we see that $\hat{\varphi}_\lambda(\cdot)$ is coercive. Also, it is sequentially weakly lower semicontinuous. Therefore, we can find $u_\lambda \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ such that

$$\hat{\varphi}_\lambda(u_\lambda) = \inf \left[\hat{\varphi}_\lambda(u) \mid u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \right] \Rightarrow \langle \hat{\varphi}'_\lambda(u_\lambda), h \rangle = 0$$

for all $h \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$. Hence, we have

$$\langle V(u_\lambda), h \rangle = \int_{\Omega} \hat{K}_\lambda(z, u_\lambda) h \, dz \quad (4.2)$$

for all $h \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$. In (4.2), first, we use the test function $h = [\bar{u}_\lambda - u_\lambda]^+ \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ to get

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle V(u_\lambda), (\bar{u}_\lambda - u_\lambda)^+ \rangle \\ &= \int_{\Omega} [\bar{u}_\lambda^{-\eta} + \lambda f(z, \bar{u}_\lambda)] (\bar{u}_\lambda - u_\lambda)^+ \, dz \quad (\text{see (4.1)}) \\ &\geq \int_{\Omega} \lambda [\eta \bar{u}_\lambda^{q-1} - c_5 \bar{u}_\lambda^{r-1}] (\bar{u}_\lambda - u_\lambda)^+ \, dz \quad (\text{see (3.1)}) \\ &= \langle V(\bar{u}_\lambda), (\bar{u}_\lambda - u_\lambda)^+ \rangle \quad (\text{see Proposition 3.1}). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, we use Proposition 2.6 to get $\bar{u}_\lambda \leq u_\lambda$.

Next, in (4.2), we choose the test function $h = [u_\lambda - \tilde{u}_\lambda]^+ \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle V(u_\lambda), (u_\lambda - \tilde{u}_\lambda)^+ \rangle \\ &= \int_{\Omega} [\tilde{u}_\lambda^{-\eta} + \lambda f(z, \tilde{u}_\lambda)] (u_\lambda - \tilde{u}_\lambda)^+ \, dz \quad (\text{see (4.1)}) \\ &\leq \int_{\Omega} \lambda [\bar{u}_\lambda^{-\eta} + 1] (u_\lambda - \tilde{u}_\lambda)^+ \, dz \quad (\text{see (3.12)}) \\ &= \langle V(\tilde{u}_\lambda), (u_\lambda - \tilde{u}_\lambda)^+ \rangle \quad (\text{see Proposition 3.2}), \end{aligned}$$

thus, $u_\lambda \leq \tilde{u}_\lambda$ due to Proposition 2.6.

So, we have proved that

$$u_\lambda \in [\bar{u}_\lambda, \tilde{u}_\lambda]. \quad (4.3)$$

From (4.1), (4.2) and (4.3), it follows that

$$u_\lambda \in S_\lambda \Rightarrow (0, \lambda_0] \subseteq \mathcal{L} \neq \emptyset.$$

Now, let $u \in S_\lambda$ and let $\mu \in (0, \lambda_0)$ be such that $0 < \mu < \lambda$. We have

$$\langle V(u), h \rangle = \int_{\Omega} [u^{-\eta} + \lambda f(z, u)] h \, dz \quad \text{for all } h \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega). \quad (4.4)$$

We introduce the Carathéodory function

$$e(z, x) := \begin{cases} \eta(x^+)^{q-1} - c_5(x^+)^{r-1} & \text{if } x \leq u(z), \\ \eta u(z)^{q-1} - c_5 u(z)^{r-1} & \text{if } u(z) < x. \end{cases} \quad (4.5)$$

We set $E(z, x) = \int_0^x e(z, s) ds$ and consider the C^1 -functional $\delta_\mu: W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined by

$$\sigma_\mu(u) := \int_\Omega G(Du) dz - \int_\Omega \mu E(z, u) dz \text{ for all } u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega).$$

From Lemma 2.2 and (4.5), it is clear that $\sigma_\mu(\cdot)$ is coercive. Also, it is sequentially weakly lower semicontinuous. So, we can find $\bar{v}_\mu \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ such that

$$\sigma_\mu(\bar{v}_\mu) = \inf \left[\sigma_\mu(u) \mid u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \right] < 0 = \sigma_\mu(0),$$

namely,

$$\langle V(\bar{v}_\mu), h \rangle = \int_\Omega \mu e(z, \bar{v}_\mu) h dz \text{ for all } h \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega), \text{ and } \bar{v}_\mu \neq 0. \quad (4.6)$$

In (4.6), first, we use $h = -\bar{v}_\mu^- \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ and obtain $\bar{v}_\mu \geq 0$ and $\bar{v}_\mu \neq 0$.

Next, in (4.6), we choose $(\bar{v}_\mu - u)^+ \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle V(\bar{v}_\mu), (\bar{v}_\mu - u)^+ \rangle \\ &= \int_\Omega \mu [\eta u^{q-1} - c_5 u^{r-1}] (\bar{v}_\mu - u)^+ dz \\ &\leq \int_\Omega [u^{-\eta} + \mu f(z, u)] (\bar{v}_\mu - u)^+ dz \text{ (see (3.1))} \\ &\leq \int_\Omega [u^{-\eta} + \lambda f(z, u)] (\bar{v}_\mu - u)^+ dz \text{ (for } \mu \in (0, \lambda) \text{ small, see Proposition 3.1)} \\ &= \langle V(u), (\bar{v}_\mu - u)^+ \rangle \text{ (see (4.4)).} \end{aligned}$$

It follows from Proposition 2.6 that $\bar{u}_\mu \leq u$. So, we have proved that

$$\bar{v}_\mu \in [0, u] \text{ and } \bar{v}_\mu \neq 0. \quad (4.7)$$

Then, (4.5), (4.6), (4.7) and Proposition 3.1 imply

$$\bar{v}_\mu = \bar{u}_\mu \Rightarrow \bar{u}_\mu \leq u \text{ (see (4.7)).}$$

From Giacomoni-Kumar-Sreenadh [7], we have that $u \in \text{int}C_+$, i.e., $S_\lambda \subseteq \text{int}C_+$. \square

A useful byproduct of the above proof is the following corollary which provides a lower bound for the elements of S_λ .

Corollary 4.2. *If hypotheses H_0 and H_1 hold, $\lambda \in \mathcal{L}$ and $\mu \in (0, \lambda)$ is small, then $\bar{u}_\mu \leq u$ for all $u \in S_\lambda$.*

Using this corollary, we can produce a smallest element for the set S_λ (minimal positive solution). First, we show that S_λ is downward directed, that is, if $u_1, u_2 \in S_\lambda$, we can find $u \in S_\lambda$ such that $u \leq u_1$ and $u \leq u_2$. We follow the argument of Lemma 4.1 of Filippakis-Papageorgiou [4].

Proposition 4.3. *If hypotheses H_0 and H_1 , hold, then for every $\lambda \in \mathcal{L}$, S_λ is downward directed.*

Proof. Let $\varepsilon > 0$ and define the function

$$\gamma_\varepsilon(s) := \begin{cases} -\varepsilon & \text{if } s < -\varepsilon, \\ s & \text{if } -\varepsilon \leq s \leq \varepsilon, \\ \varepsilon & \text{if } \varepsilon \leq s. \end{cases}$$

This is a Lipschitz continuous function. So, if $u_1, u_2 \in S_\lambda$, then

$$\gamma_\varepsilon((u_1 - u_2)^-) \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \text{ (see [15], p. 22).}$$

From the chain rule for Sobolev functions (see [15], p. 22), we have

$$D\gamma_\varepsilon((u_1 - u_2)^-) = \gamma'_\varepsilon((u_1 - u_2)^-) D(u_1 - u_2)^-.$$

Let $\theta \in C_c^1(\Omega)$ and consider the following functions

$$h_1 = \gamma_\varepsilon((u_1 - u_2)^-) \theta \text{ and } h_2 = (\varepsilon - \gamma_\varepsilon(u_1 - u_2)^-) \theta.$$

From Proposition 1.4.13, p. 25, of [15], we have

$$h_1, h_2 \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega),$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \langle V(u_1), h_1 \rangle &= \int_\Omega [u_1^{-\eta} + \lambda f(z, u_1)] h_1 dz \text{ and} \\ \langle V(u_2), h_2 \rangle &= \int_\Omega [u_2^{-\eta} + \lambda f(z, u_2)] h_2 dz. \end{aligned}$$

We add these two equalities, divide with $\varepsilon > 0$ and then let $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+$ to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \gamma_\varepsilon((u_1 - u_2)^-(z)) &\rightarrow \chi_{\{u_1 < u_2\}}(z) \text{ for a.a. } z \in \Omega, \text{ as } \varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+ \\ \text{and } \chi_{\{u_1 \geq u_2\}} &= 1 - \chi_{\{u_1 < u_2\}}. \end{aligned}$$

So, in the limit as $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+$, using Fatou's lemma, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} &\langle V(u_1), \chi_{\{u_1 < u_2\}} \theta \rangle + \langle V(u_2), \chi_{\{u_1 \geq u_2\}} \theta \rangle \\ &\geq \int_{\{u_1 < u_2\}} u_1^{-\eta} \theta dz + \int_{\{u_1 \geq u_2\}} u_2^{-\eta} \theta dz \\ &\quad + \int_{\{u_1 < u_2\}} \lambda f(z, u_1) \theta dz + \int_{\{u_1 \geq u_2\}} \lambda f(z, u_2) \theta dz. \end{aligned} \quad (4.8)$$

If $y = \min\{u_1, u_2\}$, then $y \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ and we have

$$Dy(z) = \begin{cases} Du_1(z) & \text{if } z \in \{u_1 \leq u_2\}, \\ Du_2(z) & \text{if } z \in \{u_2 \leq u_1\}, \end{cases} \quad (4.9)$$

due to [15], p. 23. From (4.8), (4.9) and the density of $C_c^1(\Omega)_+$ in $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)_+$, (here $C_c^1(\Omega)_+$ and $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)_+$ denote the cones of nonnegative elements of these spaces), we infer that y is an upper solution of (1.1). Recall that $\bar{u} \leq y$ for $\mu \in (0, \lambda)$ small (see Corollary 4.2). We introduce the Carathéodory function $e_\lambda(z, x)$ defined by

$$e_\lambda(z, x) := \begin{cases} \bar{u}_\mu(z)^{-\eta} + \lambda f(z, \bar{u}_\mu(z)) & \text{if } x < \bar{u}_\mu(z), \\ x^{-\eta} + \lambda f(z, x) & \text{if } \bar{u}_\mu \leq x \leq y(z), \\ y(z)^{-\eta} + \lambda f(z, y(z)) & \text{if } y(z) < x. \end{cases} \quad (4.10)$$

We set $E_\lambda(z, x) := \int_0^x e_\lambda(z, s) ds$ and consider the C^1 -functional $w_\lambda: W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined by

$$w_\lambda(u) := \int_\Omega G(Du) dz - \int_\Omega E_\lambda(z, u) dz \text{ for all } u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega).$$

Corollary 2.3 and (4.10) show that $w_\lambda(\cdot)$ is coercive. Also, it is sequentially weakly lower semicontinuous. So, by the Weierstrass-Tonelli theorem, we can find $u_\lambda \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ such that

$$w_\lambda(u_\lambda) = \inf \left[w_\lambda(u) \mid u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \right] \Rightarrow \langle w'_\lambda(u_\lambda), h \rangle = 0 \text{ for all } h \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega).$$

This means that

$$\langle V(u_\lambda), h \rangle = \int_{\Omega} e_\lambda(z, u_\lambda) h \, dz \text{ for all } h \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega). \quad (4.11)$$

In (4.11), first, we choose $h = [\bar{u}_\mu - u_\lambda]^+ \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ to get

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle V(u_\lambda), (\bar{u}_\mu - u_\lambda)^+ \rangle \\ &= \int_{\Omega} [\bar{u}_\mu^{-\eta} + \lambda f(z, \bar{u}_\mu)] (\bar{u}_\mu - u_\lambda)^+ \, dz \\ &\geq \int_{\Omega} \lambda f(z, \bar{u}_\mu) (\bar{u}_\mu - u_\lambda)^+ \, dz \\ &\geq \int_{\Omega} \mu f(z, \bar{u}_\mu) (\bar{u}_\mu - u_\lambda)^+ \, dz \text{ (since } f(z, \bar{u}_\mu) \geq 0 \\ &\quad \text{for all } \mu \in (0, \lambda) \text{ small, see Proposition 3.1)} \\ &\geq \int_{\Omega} \mu [\eta \bar{u}_\mu^{q-1} - c_5 \bar{u}_\mu^{r-1}] (\bar{u}_\mu - u_\lambda)^+ \, dz \text{ (see (3.1))} \\ &= \langle V(\bar{u}_\mu), (\bar{u}_\mu - u_\lambda)^+ \rangle \text{ (see Proposition 3.1).} \end{aligned}$$

Hence, by Proposition 2.6, we have $\bar{u}_\mu \leq u_\lambda$.

Next, in (4.11), we use the test function $h = [u_\lambda - y]^+ \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle V(u_\lambda), (u_\lambda - y)^+ \rangle \\ &= \int_{\Omega} [y^{-\eta} + \lambda f(z, y)] (u_\lambda - y)^+ \, dz \text{ (see (4.10))} \\ &\leq \langle V(y), (u_\lambda - y)^+ \rangle \text{ (recall } y \text{ is an upper solution of (1.1), see (4.8)).} \end{aligned}$$

This together with Proposition 2.6 reveals that $u_\lambda \leq y$. So, we have proved that

$$u_\lambda \in [\bar{u}_\mu, y]. \quad (4.12)$$

Then, (4.10), (4.11) and (4.12) imply that

$$u_\lambda \in S_\lambda \subseteq \text{int}C_+ \text{ and } v_\lambda \leq y \text{ (see (4.12)),}$$

namely, S_λ is downward directed. \square

Using Proposition 4.3, we can produce the minimal positive solution.

Proposition 4.4. *If hypotheses H_0 and H_1 hold and $\lambda \in \mathcal{L}$, then problem (1.1) has a smallest positive solution*

$$u_\lambda^* \in S_\lambda \subseteq \text{int}C_+.$$

Proof. From Theorem 5.109, p. 309, of Hu-Papageorgiou [9], we can find $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq S_\lambda$ decreasing (since S_λ is downward directed, see Proposition 4.3) such that

$$\inf S_\lambda = \inf_{n \in \mathbb{N}} u_n.$$

We have

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle V(u_n), h \rangle \\ &= \int_{\Omega} [u_n^{-\eta} + \lambda f(z, u_n)] h \, dz \text{ for all } h \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \text{ and for all } n \in \mathbb{N}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.13)$$

Hence,

$$\bar{u}_\mu \leq u_n \leq u_1 \text{ for } \mu \in (0, \lambda) \text{ (see Corollary 4.2)}. \quad (4.14)$$

In (4.13), we choose $h = u_n \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$. Using (4.14), hypothesis $H_1(i)$ and Lemma 2.2, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{c_0}{p-1} \|u_n\|^p \leq c_{20} \text{ for some } c_{20} > 0, \\ & \text{all } n \in \mathbb{N}, \Rightarrow \{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \text{ is bounded.} \end{aligned}$$

So, we may assume that

$$u_n \xrightarrow{w} u_\lambda^* \text{ in } W_0^{1,p} \text{ and } u_n \rightarrow u_\lambda^* \text{ in } L^p(\Omega). \quad (4.15)$$

In (4.13), we use the test function $h = u_n - u_\lambda^* \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$, pass to the limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$ and use (4.15) to obtain

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle V(u_n), u_n - u_\lambda^* \rangle = 0 \Rightarrow u_n \rightarrow u_\lambda^* \text{ in } W_0^{1,p}(\Omega). \quad (4.16)$$

From (4.14), we have

$$u_n^{-\eta} \leq \bar{u}_\mu^{-\eta}. \quad (4.17)$$

Recall that $\bar{u}_\mu \in \text{int}C_+$ (see Proposition 3.1). So, we can find $c_{21} > 0$ such that

$$c_{21} \hat{d} \leq u_\mu. \quad (4.18)$$

Then, for all $h \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\Omega} \left(\frac{|h|}{u_n} \right)^p dz \\ & \leq \int_{\Omega} \left(\frac{|h|}{\bar{u}_\mu} \right)^p dz \text{ (see (4.17))} \\ & = \int_{\Omega} \bar{u}_\mu^{(1-\eta)p} \left(\frac{|h|}{\bar{u}_\mu} \right)^p dz \\ & \leq c_{22} \int_{\Omega} \left(\frac{|h|}{\hat{d}} \right)^p dz \text{ for some } c_{22} > 0 \text{ (recall that } \bar{u}_\mu \in \text{int}C_+ \text{ and (4.18))} \\ & \leq c_{23} \|Dh\|_p^p \text{ for some } c_{23} > 0, \end{aligned}$$

where the last inequality is obtained by using Hardy's inequality, see [19], p. 66.

Hence, $\left\{ \frac{h}{u_n} \right\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq L^p(\Omega)$ is bounded.

Also, from (4.16), we have (at least for a subsequence) that

$$\left(\frac{h}{u_n} \right)(z) \rightarrow \left(\frac{h}{u_\lambda^*} \right)(z) \text{ for a.a. } z \in \Omega.$$

Therefore, from Problem 1.44 of Gasiński-Papageorgiou [6], we have

$$\int_{\Omega} u_n^{-\eta} h \, dz \rightarrow \int_{\Omega} (u_\lambda^*)^{-\eta} h \, dz \Rightarrow \langle V(u_\lambda^*), h \rangle = \int_{\Omega} [(u_\lambda^*)^{-\eta} + \lambda f(z, u_\lambda^*)] h \, dz$$

for all $h \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ (see (4.16)). Since $\bar{u}_\mu \leq u_\lambda^*$ (see (4.14)), it follows that $u_\lambda^* \in S_\lambda$, that is, $u_\lambda^* = \inf S_\lambda$. \square

Remark 4.5. Clearly $u_\lambda^* \rightarrow 0$ in $C_0^1(\bar{\Omega})$ as $\lambda \rightarrow 0^+$.

For $\lambda \in (0, \lambda_0]$, we have a pair of positive solutions.

Proposition 4.6. *If hypotheses H_0 and H_1 hold and $\lambda \in (0, \lambda_0]$, then problem (1.1) has at least two positive solutions $u_0, \hat{u} \in \text{int}C_+$.*

Proof. From the proof of Proposition 4.1, we know that there is $u_0 \in S_\lambda \subseteq \text{int}C_+$ minimizer of $\varphi_\lambda(\cdot)$ such that

$$u_0 \in [\bar{u}_\mu, \tilde{u}_\lambda]. \quad (4.19)$$

Let $\rho = \|\tilde{u}_\lambda\|_\infty$ and let $\hat{\xi}_\rho > 0$ be as postulated by hypothesis $H_1(\text{iv})$. Then, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & -\text{diva}(Dv_0) + \lambda \hat{\xi}_\rho u_0^{p-1} - u_0^{-\eta} \\ & = \lambda f(z, u_0) + \lambda \hat{\xi}_\rho u_0^{p-1} \\ & \geq \lambda f(z, \bar{u}_\lambda) + \lambda \hat{\xi}_\rho \bar{u}_\lambda^{p-1} \text{ (see (4.19) and hypothesis } H_1(\text{iv})) \\ & \geq \lambda \left[\eta \bar{u}_\lambda^{q-1} - c_5 \bar{u}_\lambda^{r-1} \right] + \lambda \hat{\xi}_\rho \bar{u}_\lambda^{p-1} \text{ (see (3.1))} \\ & \geq -\text{diva}(D\bar{u}_\lambda) + \lambda \hat{\xi}_\rho \bar{u}_\lambda^{p-1} - \bar{u}_\lambda^{-\eta} \text{ in } \Omega \text{ (see Proposition 3.1)}. \end{aligned}$$

The latter combined with Proposition 7 of [16] and the fact $\bar{u}_\lambda \in \text{int}C_+$ implies $u_0 - \bar{u}_\lambda \in \text{int}C_+$.

Similarly, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & -\text{diva}(Du_0) + \lambda \hat{\xi}_\rho u_0^{p-1} - u_0^{-\eta} \\ & = \lambda f(z, u_0) + \lambda \hat{\xi}_\rho u_0^{p-1} \\ & \leq \lambda f(z, \tilde{u}_\lambda) + \lambda \hat{\xi}_\rho \tilde{u}_\lambda^{p-1} \text{ (see (4.19) and hypothesis } H_1(\text{iv})) \\ & \leq 1 + \lambda \hat{\xi}_\rho \tilde{u}_\lambda^{p-1} \text{ (see (3.12))} \\ & = -\text{diva}(D\tilde{u}_\lambda) + \lambda \hat{\xi}_\rho \tilde{u}_\lambda^{p-1} - \tilde{u}_\lambda^{-\eta} \\ & \leq -\text{diva}(D\tilde{u}_\lambda) + \lambda \hat{\xi}_\rho \tilde{u}_\lambda^{p-1} - \tilde{u}_\lambda^{-\eta} \text{ (see Proposition 3.3)}. \end{aligned}$$

So, by (3.12) and Proposition 7 of [16], we obtain $\tilde{u}_\lambda - u_0 \in \text{int}C_+$. This means that

$$u_0 \in \text{int}_{C_0^1(\bar{\Omega})} [\bar{u}_\mu, \tilde{u}_\lambda]. \quad (4.20)$$

We introduce the Carathéodory function $l_\lambda(z, x)$ defined by

$$l_\lambda(z, x) := \begin{cases} \bar{u}_\mu(z)^{-\eta} + \lambda f(z, \bar{u}_\mu(z)) & \text{if } x \leq \bar{u}_\mu(z), \\ x^{-\eta} + \lambda f(z, x) & \text{if } \bar{u}_\mu(z) < x. \end{cases} \quad (4.21)$$

We set $L_\lambda(z, x) = \int_0^x l_\lambda(z, s) ds$ and consider the C^1 -functional $\varphi_\lambda: W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined by

$$\varphi_\lambda(u) := \int_\Omega G(Du) dz - \int_\Omega L_\lambda(z, u) dz \text{ for all } u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega).$$

From (4.1) and (4.21), we see that

$$\varphi_\lambda \Big|_{[\bar{u}_\nu, \bar{u}_\lambda]} = \hat{\varphi}_\lambda \Big|_{[\bar{u}_\mu, \bar{u}_\lambda]}. \quad (4.22)$$

Recall that u_0 is a global minimizer of $\hat{\varphi}_\lambda(\cdot)$ (see the proof of Proposition 4.1). Then, from (4.20) and (4.22), it follows that u_0 is a local $C_0^1(\bar{\Omega})$ -minimizer of φ_λ , namely,

$$u_0 \text{ is a local } W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)\text{-minimizer of } \varphi_\lambda(\cdot) \quad (4.23)$$

due to Proposition A3 of Papageorgiou-Rădulescu-Zhang [17]. Using (3.1) and (4.21), we can easily show that

$$K_{\varphi_\lambda} \subseteq [\bar{u}_\mu] \cap \text{int}C_+. \quad (4.24)$$

Therefore, we may assume that K_{φ_λ} is finite, otherwise from (4.21) and (4.24), we see that (1.1) has an infinity of distinct positive solutions and so we are done. From (4.23) and using Theorem 5.7.6, p. 449, of Papageorgiou-Rădulescu-Repovš [15], we can find $\rho \in (0, 1)$ small such that

$$\varphi_\lambda(u_0) < \inf [\varphi_\lambda(u) \mid \|u - u_0\| = \rho] = m_\lambda. \quad (4.25)$$

On account of hypothesis H_1 (ii), if $u \in \text{int}C_+$, then we have

$$\varphi_\lambda(tu) \rightarrow -\infty \text{ as } t \rightarrow +\infty. \quad (4.26)$$

Moreover, reasoning as in the ‘‘Claim’’ in the proof of Proposition 4 of [17], we show that

$$\varphi_\lambda(\cdot) \text{ satisfies the } C\text{-condition}. \quad (4.27)$$

Then, (4.25), (4.26) and (4.27), permit the use of the mountain pass theorem and obtain $\hat{u} \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ such that

$$\hat{u} \in K_{\varphi_\lambda} \subseteq [\bar{u}_\mu] \cap \text{int}C_+ \text{ (see (4.24)) and } \varphi_\lambda(u_0) < m_\lambda \leq \varphi_\lambda(\bar{u}) \text{ (see (4.25))}.$$

So, $\hat{u} \in \text{int}C_+$ is a second positive solution of (1.1) which is distinct from u_0 . \square

Summarizing our findings, we can state the following theorem concerning the existence and multiplicity of positive solutions for problem (1.1).

Theorem 4.7. *If hypotheses H_0 and H_1 hold, then for all $\lambda > 0$ small, we have*

- *problem (1.1) has at least two positive solutions $u_0, \hat{u} \in \text{int}C_+$.*
- *problem (1.1) has a smallest positive solution $u_\lambda^* \in \text{int}C_+$.*
- *$u_\lambda^* \rightarrow 0$ in $C_0^1(\bar{\Omega})$ as $\lambda \rightarrow 0^+$.*

Remark 4.8. Is it possible to have an existence and multiplicity result which is global in $\lambda > 0$ (a bifurcation-type theorem) as in the case of problems with positive perturbation (see [1, 16, 18])? The fact that perturbation $f(z, x)$ is sign changing, creates difficulties and prohibits the use of the techniques used in [1, 16, 18].

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